

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DIAGNOSIS OF BREAST GLANDS IN PREMENOPAUSAL WOMEN

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ДИАГНОСТИКА МОЛОЧНЫХ ЖЕЛЕЗ У ЖЕНЩИН ПРЕМЕНОПАУЗАЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Abstract

Premenopausal women were examined ; non-palpable mammary gland formations were detected in (15.8%) women, of which (30.5%) cases of cancer were verified. The information content of standard mammography and ultrasound after the use of diagnostic mammography increased by 5%. Significant criteria for malignancy and indications for biopsy were identified. The results obtained indicate the need for mandatory use of diagnostic mammography, digital mammography and mammoscintigraphy with the domestic tumor-tropic drug “^{99m}Tc-technetrit”. For radiation examinations in premenopausal women , digital mammography and mammoscintigraphy are sensitive diagnostic methods that give positive results for the treatment of breast cancer in women.

Аннотация

Обследовано женщины пременопаузального возраста, у (15,8%) женщин выявлены не пальпируемые образования молочных желез, из которых верифицировано (30,5%) случаев рака. Информативность стандартной маммографии и УЗИ после применения диагностической маммографии увеличилась на 5%. Выделены значимые критерии злокачественного образования и показания к биопсии. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о необходимости обязательного применения диагностической маммографии цифровой маммографии и маммосцинтиграфии с отечественным опухолетропным препаратом «^{99m}Tc-технетрил». При лучевом обследовании у женщин в пременопаузе, методы цифровой маммографии и маммосцинтиграфии являются чувствительным методом диагностики, которые дают положительные результаты для лечения РМЖ у женщин

Keywords: Mammography, multicentric breast cancer , and mammoscintigraphy .

Ключевые слова: Маммография, рак молочной железы мультицентричный, и маммосцинтиграфия.

Introduction

Breast cancer (BC) currently ranks first in the structure of cancer morbidity and mortality among all malignant neoplasms in women [1, 2], but there are more than two million cases of breast cancer and deaths in the world. This is due, first of all, to the low detection of tumors in the early stages of the disease [3,4]. Fundamental epidemiological studies can help us identify breast cancer in the preclinical phase, preventing breast cancer by blocking the most serious risk factors [5]. The geography of breast cancer distribution is also heterogeneous. The highest incidence rates are among

women living in Hawaii, British Columbia and California. In these areas, the incidence rate is almost 80-90 cases per 100,000 women. The smallest number of cases occurs in Japan, where breast cancer occurs in only 12-15 cases per 100,000 women [5].

The incidence of the disease is also heterogeneous among women of different social classes. Thus, according to Finnish authors, the greatest risk of developing breast cancer is in women of high social class, so to speak, the price to pay for a prosperous life [5]. Reducing the level of morbidity, especially mortality, is the

main goal of all epidemiological, clinical, and genetic studies.

It is known that early diagnosis of breast cancer makes a significant contribution to increasing the effectiveness of treatment for this category of patients, on the one hand, providing conditions for reducing the aggressiveness of treatment and reducing the risk of com-

plications of antitumor therapy, on the other hand, creating the prerequisites for achieving higher rates of overall and without relapse survival rate [6,7].

Analyzing the capabilities of standard and additional methods of breast cancer and ultrasound in complex diagnostics, identifying significant signs of breast cancer and predictors of the use of invasive diagnostic techniques is currently a necessary method for the early diagnosis of patients with breast cancer (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Algorithm for examining patients for early diagnosis of patients with breast cancer.

Diagnosis of breast cancer and breast cancer was performed using the Mammomat -3000 Nova device , Siemens . Diagnostic punctures were performed with a MAGNUM biopsy gun.

According to RMG data, LMWH were detected in the form of: space-occupying formations (OO) up to 15 mm in size (70.2%), local heaviness (LT = 7.1%), microcalcifications (MCC = 17.9%), density asymmetry (4, 7%). The information content of standard RMG was limited by: high radiological density of the breast (n = 32), small size of formations (<5 mm; n = 38) and MCC (n = 53), the effect of superposition of structures (n = 29), which required the use of additional RMG techniques in 8.7% of cases. Reliably benign characteristics of category BI-RADS – 2 were diagnosed in 294 (69.5%) patients. The most common OOs were: fibroadenomas (FA, n = 77), cysts (n = 114), lipomas (n = 12), foci of fibrosis (n = 20), hamartomas (n = 6). In 124 (29%) cases, lesions reliably detected by RMG were sononegative, these are: OO less than 5 mm (n = 38), LT areas (n = 33), grouped by MCC (n = 53). Morphological verification was carried out in all cases of NMG. We performed 199 sectoral resections (FA - 57 (29%), proliferation area - 25 (12%), complex cyst - 10 (5%), MCC - 50 (25%), fibrosis - 24 (13%), suspicion of breast cancer – 31 (16%); 153 Cor biopsies (under ultrasound control – 96 (62%) and under Rg navigation – 57 (38%), 59 fine needle biopsies (FNA) under ultrasound navigation.

When comparing the radiation characteristics and the results of a morphological study, for convenience of practical use, we identified the most important, in our

opinion, RMG and ultrasound signs, which have the greatest consistency in frequency of occurrence in cases of suspected breast cancer, the reliability of which is confirmed by the results of histological examination. For OO: irregular shape (n = 71), radiant contours (n = 56), high density (n = 42); non-parallel orientation (n = 68), unclear contours (n = 44), hypervascularization (n = 48). For RT: stellate shape (n=8), calcifications (n=4), hypervascularization (n=6). For breast cancer when visualizing OO (n = 76), the highest correlation according to RMG data was noted between the shape – stellate (n = 71), contour – spicule-like (n = 56); for MCC (n = 53) between indeterminate shape (n = 46) and linear distribution (n = 24). At the same time, significant radiological signs were more often determined in combination and most confidently identified when interpreting diagnostic RMG images, increasing the information content of the method by 5%, which dictates the need for their mandatory use. Newly identified lesions (during primary RMG) without pathognomic Rg - signs of malignancy according to standard RMG and ultrasound, categorized as BI-RADS - 3 (n = 57), in 96% of cases (n = 54) after interpretation of an additional examination.

Women of reproductive age were examined in the first phase of the menstrual cycle from 5 to 12 days from the beginning of the cycle.

In all examined patients, morphological verification of changes in the mammary gland was performed. In 81% of patients, the presence of a malignant for-

mation was detected, and in 19%, the absence of pathological changes or the presence of a benign formation (Figure 2).

Morphological verification of changes in the mammary glands revealed invasive ductal carcinoma, in (12.3%) – non-invasive intraductal carcinoma (in

situ), in 16 (3.6%) - lobular carcinoma, in (1.8%) - invasive ductal carcinoma with a predominance of the intraductal component, in (1%) - mucinous carcinoma, in (0.2%) - tubular carcinoma, in (4.6%) - fibroadenoma and in the remaining (11.5%) cases - localized adeno-

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Fig.2 – Distribution of studied women into groups for early diagnosis of breast cancer patients according to the density of various formations.

The examination of both mammary glands was performed 10–15 minutes after intravenous administration of the domestic tumor-tropic drug “^{99m}Tctechnetritl”. Visualization of both mammary glands was carried out in lateral and anterior projections. X-ray density of breast tissue is shown in Fig. 3

Fig. 3. X-ray density of breast tissue.

Mammoscintigraphy was carried out in planar mode on a Forte (Philips) emission computed tomograph with two rectangular detectors equipped with low-energy, highly sensitive collimators (Fig. 4).

Fig.4. Emission computed tomograph device" Forte (Philips)"

To avoid overlapping images of the mammary glands in the lateral projection, the study was carried out as follows: a special pillow with a lead insert was placed between the mammary glands, and the gamma camera detectors, equipped with parallel high-resolution collimators for an energy of 140 KeV, were located in the lateral projections (at an angle of 90 and 270 degrees) in close proximity to the mammary glands.

Reconstruction and processing of the obtained images was carried out on a workstation using a Hanning filter. In the process of analyzing the reconstructed image, the filter parameters were selected individually. The evaluation of the obtained scintigrams was carried out in accordance with the following criteria: presence/absence of areas of hyperfixation tumor-tropic radiopharmaceuticals in the mammary glands, the intensity and uniformity of distribution of radiopharmaceuticals in the foci of hyperfixation, the shape of the detected changes (correct, irregular), boundaries (clear, fuzzy). In patients with hyperfixation of radiopharmaceuticals in the mammary glands, a semi-quantitative indicator of the intensity of hyperfixation of radiopharmaceuticals was calculated [8], which was determined as the ratio of the specific number of impulses in the area of the focus of radiopharmaceutical hyperfixation to the specific number of impulses in the adjacent areas of the unchanged breast (tumor/background index). In the presence of several foci located in different quadrants of the breast, the multicentric nature of the tumor process was established.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

The most sensitive method for diagnosing breast cancer in women is the combined use of digital mammography and mammoscintigraphy with the domestic tumor-tropic drug ^{99m}Tc-technetritl".

To reduce the number of errors in the diagnosis of minimal and multicentric breast cancer, it is necessary

to use not only digital mammography, but also mammoscintigraphy.

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